

BIODEGRADABLE POLYESTER MATRIX REINFORCED WITH HEMP FIBRES – EFFECT OF FIBRE REFINEMENT BY STEAM EXPLOSION

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SUMMARY: A biodegradable copolyester was compounded in a twinscrew extruder with 25 wt% hemp fibres and then injection moulded into tensile test bars. Two different types of fibres were used: An exclusively mechanically treated fibre (MEC) and a fibre refined by steam explosion (STE). The mechanical properties of STE fibres are 30 % lower than those of MEC fibres, nevertheless the same reinforcing effect was obtained. This is mainly due to the higher aspect ratio of STE and the better fibre distribution in the STE composites. A maximal reinforcement was not achieved, because of a too weak fibre matrix adhesion in combination with an insufficient fibre length caused by fibre damage in the extrusion and injection moulding process.

KEYWORDS: biodegradable, copolyester, steam explosion, hemp fibre.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing environmental awareness and decreasing dump space lead to the search for new polymer recycling and disposal possibilities [1,2]. So far 25 million tons of plastic waste are accumulated annually world-wide [3]. To reduce polymer waste, compostable, biologically degradable polymers represent an interesting alternative to conventional plastics. Recently developed biodegradable polymers are used to produce composting bags and packaging materials [4,5]. Fibre reinforcement would make it possible for these materials to be used as lightweight construction materials as well. Vegetable fibres, especially bast fibres, e.g. hemp or flax fibres, are suitable for this purpose. Their weight specific mechanical properties are comparable to those of glass fibres [6-9]. They are less abrasive than glass fibres, which would result in lower tooling costs and higher productivity. During combustion, bast fibres do not lead to clinker formation, clinker having to be disposed of. Among bast fibres, hemp is the most interesting agronomic cultivation choice for middle European climates. An average fibre yield of 3.6 t/ha is achieved over a cultivation period of 4 months. Hemp is a very competitive culture, demanding neither herbicides nor fungicides [11,12]. New technologies for a

competitive production of mechanically decorticated hemp bast have been developed and production plants realised. The resulting bast fibre bundles are used as insulation material or to reinforce compression moulded parts [13,14]. Degumming technologies for fibre refinement were also developed in view of the fibres being processed on cotton spinning machines. Degumming chemically or enzymatically removes gum substances such as lignin, pectin, and hemicellulose which glue the single fibres together. Such degummed fibres seem to be promising for the reinforcement of composite materials [15,16]. They have much smaller fibre diameters (5 to 50 μm) compared to only mechanically decorticated (MEC) fibre bundles [16]. Their cellulose surface is mostly free of gum components which can decompose during processing at temperatures above 200°C [17]. An effective method for fibre degumming is the steam explosion technology (STE). In the steam explosion process the decorticated raw fibre bundles are treated in a pressure chamber, using saturated alkalic steam at a pressure of up to 12 bar. After an impregnation time of several minutes a sudden release of pressure causes the fibre bundles to elementarize [18]. The present investigation deals with reinforcement of a biodegradable copolyester by hemp fibres degummed by means of steam explosion in comparison to reinforcement achieved by solely mechanically decorticated fibre bundles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Polymer

The polymer used as matrix material was Copolyester 14766 which is manufactured by Eastman Chemical Company. It is a biodegradable polymer produced from conventional diacids and glycols. Its properties are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of Copolyester 14766-film of 2mm thickness.

Density	1.27	g/cm^3
Crystalline Tm	112	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Tg	-33	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Tensile Strength	19	MPa
Elongation at Break	600	%
Tensile Modulus of Elasticity	97	MPa

Fibres

The fibres processed were hemp fibres of the "Futura 77" variety, which had been mechanically treated on a decortivating device Flaksy® (Bahmer Maschinenbau GmbH) following 20 days of field retting (MEC). MEC treated fibres build fibre bundles of 20 to 50 single fibres in the cross section, glued together with gum substances such as pectin, lignin, and hemicelluloses (see Fig. 1). The chemical composition of such fibres is described in Table 2.

Table 2: Chemical Composition of mechanically decorticated hemp fibres [19].

Component	wt%
Cellulose	67.0
Hemicellulose	16.1
Pectine	0.8
Lignine	3.3
Proteins, Ash and Minerals	2.1
Fats and Waxes	0.7
Humidity	10.0

The length of the fibre bundles was 20 to 100 mm. Furthermore, hemp fibres treated by steam explosion (STE) were used as matrix reinforcement. The STE treated fibres are well separated. Their cellulosic surface is free from the major part of gum substances and appears smoother than the surface of MEC treated fibres (see Fig. 1). The length of the separated fibres was 5 to 50 mm.

Fig. 1: Left: SEM picture of MEC treated fibres. 20 to 50 single fibres are glued together by gum substances, building fibre bundles. Right: STE treated fibres are well separated by removal of the major part of the gum substance. Their surface appears smoother than the surface of MEC treated fibres.

Mechanically treated hemp fibres have a tensile strength of 500-1000 MPa [19], whereas steam explosion fibres have a 30% lower strength than the mechanically treated ones [18]. The elongation at break of mechanically treated hemp fibres is 1-6% [19]. The tensile modulus of elasticity from hemp fibres in general is estimated to be from 30 to 90 GPa [8]. Their density is assumed to be 1.5 g/cm³ [19].

Extrusion

The fibres and the polymer were dried at 60 °C under vacuum during 16 h. Compounding was carried out on a Brabender PL 2100-6 co-rotating twinscrew extruder. The processing parameters are listed in Table 3. The fibres were spun to cords of a specific weight of 1,2 g/m. The extruder screws had a simple configuration without any mixing elements. After a section of polymer homogenisation of 270 mm of length the fibres were drawn into the extruder automatically by the screw rotation, which enabled a regular fibre dosage. The subsequent compounding section had a length of 260 mm. The extrusion die had a diameter of 6 mm. The fibre to polymer ratio was controlled by the amount of polymer feed (30 g/min.) and the speed of screw rotation (80 min⁻¹), so that a fibre content of 25 wt% was achieved. The extruded composite was air cooled and granulated in a granulating mill.

Table 3: Compounding parameters of the co-rotating twinscrew extruder.

Screw diameter	25 mm
L/d ratio	22 D
Die diameter [mm]	6
Fibre feeding	after 270 mm section of polymer homogenisation
Temperatures [°C] (zone 1-5)	170/177/185/177/170
Screw Speed [min ⁻¹]	80

Injection Moulding

Injection moulding of tensile test bars was carried out on a Ferromatik Milacron K40/80 injection moulding machine, by means of a K30 injection device. The processing parameters are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Processing parameters of injection moulding on Ferromatik Milacron K40/80.

Screw diameter	25 mm
L/d ratio	24 D
Compression ratio of the screw	2.03
Temperatures [°C] (zone 1-4)	150/160/170/170
Injection pressure [bar]	60
Holding pressure [bar]	75
Tool Temperature [°C]	18
Cooling Time [s]	15

Tensile Testing

Tensile testing was carried out on a "Zwick Universal Testing Machine 1456", with a cross head speed of 2 mm/min at room temperature with a relative humidity of 65%. The geometry of the tensile testing is described in Fig. 2. The modulus of elasticity was calculated at the elongation of 1 to 3 %. For each material 5 bars were measured.

Fig. 2: Geometry of the injection moulded tensile test bars.

Fibre length distribution

The fibre length distribution in the polymer granules and the tensile test bars was investigated by dissolving the samples in tetrahydrofuran at room temperature. Then the fibres were separated from the solution by filtration and then distributed on a water surface. Pictures of distributed fibres were analysed by image analysis. For this purpose the perimeter P of the photographic representation of each fibre was automatically measured with the program "ImagePro2". Fibre length was calculated as $P/2$. The contribution of the fibre ends to the perimeter was neglected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The yield strength of copolyester 14766 could be improved by hemp fibre reinforcement (25 wt%) from 6.2 to 12.8 MPa (STE) , that is to say to 13.7 MPa (MEC). The E-modulus increased from 69 to 248 MPa and to 274 MPa respectively (see Fig. 3). In both composites, non-linear behaviour of the stress-strain curves was noted, which means that the matrix properties are highly dominant (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 3: Mechanical properties of tensile test bars made of copolyester 14766 and reinforced by STE treated or MEC treated hemp fibres.

Fig. 4: Stress-strain curves of tensile test bars made of copolyester 14766 and reinforced by STE treated or MEC treated hemp fibres.

Although the tensile strength of STE fibres are 30 % lower than those of MEC fibres, almost the same reinforcement effect could be achieved, this may be due to a better distribution of the STE treated fibres in the matrix. The fibre bundles of MEC fibres were not dispersed by the extrusion and injection moulding processes, as can be seen on the fracture surface of the composites in Fig. 5. Furthermore the STE treated single fibres lead to a better aspect ratio than the fibre bundles of MEC treated fibres, which leads to a higher surface for fibre-matrix adhesion. The elongation at break in the composite containing STE treated fibres was still 248 %; whereas it was only 26 % for the composite reinforced by MEC treated fibres. This is due to fibre agglomeration caused by the remaining fibre bundles that act as a weak link.

Fig. 5: The SEM picture on the left shows a fracture surface of a copolyester tensile testing bar reinforced with 25 wt% MEC fibres. The single fibres of the bundles were not dispersed by polymer processing; whereas the fibres are well dispersed in the STE fibre composite (on the right).

The fibre-matrix adhesion seems to be low. No matrix residues can be seen on the fibres which were pulled out of the matrix and the remaining holes have the same smooth surface as the fibres (Fig. 5). Additionally the fibre length distribution of STE fibre composites shows that the fibres of an original length of 5 to 50 mm were shortened to an average length of 0.28 mm during processing (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: The mechanical stress during extrusion leads to a short average fibre length of 0.31 mm in the STE fibre composite granules. After injection moulding, the fibre lengths decrease again to an average of 0.28 mm.

CONCLUSIONS

A maximal reinforcement was not achieved, because of a weak fibre-matrix adhesion in combination with insufficient fibre lengths in the composites. The reduction of the fibres' length took place during extrusion and the injection moulding process. The fibres of the MEC bundles were shortened but not separated, which - due to the resulting low aspect ratio - caused a decrease of elongation at break of the MEC composites. The degumming of the fibres leads to a better aspect ratio, because of the separation of the single hemp fibres. To make use of the good hemp fibre properties, the average fibre length has to be increased. This can be achieved by means of less destructive processing. Furthermore, fibre-matrix adhesion

must be increased. This could be achieved by chemical modification of the cellulosic fibre surface.

REFERENCES

1. Huang S. J., "Polymer Waste Management - Biodegradation, Incineration and Recycling". *Degradable polymers, recycling and plastics waste management*. Albertsson, A.-C. and Huang, S.J., Ed. New York 1995, pp. 1-7.
2. Steinbüchel A., "Use of Biosynthetic, Biodegradable Thermoplastics and Elastomers from Renewable Resources: The Pros and Cons". *Degradable polymers, recycling and plastics waste management*. Albertsson, A.-C. and Huang, S.J., Ed. New York 1995, pp. 61-68.
3. Lee, Sang Yup, "Bacterial Polyhydroxyalkanoates", *Biotechnology and Bioengineering* Vol. 49, 1996, pp. 1-14.
4. Chandra, R. and Rustgi, R, "Biodegradable Polymers", *Progress in Polymer Science* Vol. 23, 1998, pp. 1273-1335.
5. Swift G., "Non-Medical Biodegradable Polymers", *Handbook of Biodegradable Polymers*, Domb, A.J., Kost, J., Wiseman, D.M, Ed., 1997, pp. 473-511.
6. Nickel J., Riedel U. und Herrmann A. S., "Bio-Composites - New Construction Materials Derived From Biomass". *Biomass for Energy and Industry*, 8. – 11.6.1998, pp. 79-85.
7. Kohler R. und Wedler M., "Einsatz von Flachs für faserverstärkte Kunststoffe unter Ausnutzung der spezifischen Fasereigenschaften". *Agrarforschung Baden-Württemberg - Forschungsreport VI*, 1997, pp. 45-46.
8. Kohler, J., "Bastfasern für technische Zwecke", *PdN-Bio* Vol. 77, No. 2, 1998.
9. Bledzki, A. K., Gassan, J. and Reihmane, S., "Properties and Modification Methods for Vegetable Fibers for Natural Fiber Composites", *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 59, 1996, pp. 1329-1336.
10. Hague, J., "Composites from Non-Wood Materials", *Agricultural Engineer*, No. 3, 1995, pp. 24-28.
11. Bassetti P et. al., "Hanfanbau in der Schweiz - Geschichte, aktuelle Situation, Sorten, Anbau- und Erntetechnik, wirtschaftliche Aspekte und Perspektiven", *FAT-Bericht* Nr. 516, 1998.
12. Bocsa I. und Karus M., *Der Hanfanbau - Botanik, Sorten, Anbau und Ernte*. 1. Auflage. C.F. Müller Verlag, Heidelberg, 1997.
13. Hesch R. et. al., "Hanf - Perspektiven für eine ökologische Zukunft, eine realistische Betrachtung", Taoasis Verlag GmbH, Lemgo (D), 1997.
14. Fürll, C., Hempel, H., and Baldauf, H., "Fasergrobaufschluss bei Hanf". *Landtechnik* Vol. 53 No. 1, 1998, pp. 12-13.
15. Kohler R. und Kessler R., "Einfluss der Aufschlussverfahren auf die Eigenschaften naturfaserverstärkter Kunststoffe", *International Wood and Natural Fibre Composites Symposium*, Kassel, 1998.
16. Vignon, M. R., Dupeyre, D., and Garcia-Jaldon, C., "Morphological characterization of steam-exploded hemp fibers and their utilization in polypropylene-based composites", *Bioresource Technology*, Vol. 58, 1996, pp. 203-215.

17. Hornsby, P. R., Hinrichsen, E., and Tarverdi, K., "Preparation and properties of polypropylene composites reinforced with wheat and flax straw fibres, Part I Fibre characterization", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 32 No. 2, 1997, pp. 443-449.
18. Nebel, K.M., "New Processing Strategies for Hemp", *Journal of the International Hemp Association*, No. 3, 1995.
19. Satlow, G., Zaremba, S., and Wulfhorst, B., "Flachs sowie andere Bast- und Hartfasern", *Chemiefasern/Textilindustrie* . Vol 96, No. 44, 1994, pp. 765-785.